

Sample Search Strategy

Title: Parent-level barriers and facilitators to second or subsequent dose uptake in childhood vaccination: A mixed-methods systematic review protocol

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The following is an example of a search strategy used to search for literature on CINAHL (via Ovid):

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((MH (Immunization)) OR (XB (vaccin* or vaccinat* or immuniz* or immunis*))) AND ((MH (child, preschool)) OR (XB (newborn or infant* or baby or toddler or child* or pediatric or paediatric))) AND ((MH (parents)) OR (MH (caregivers)) OR (MH (guardianship, legal)) OR (XB (parent* or mother* or father* or guardian* or caregiver))) AND ((MH (attitude to vaccines)) OR (XB (barrier* or obstacle or difficult* or challenge or facilitat* or motivat* or enabl* or hesitan*)))
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